

IOT IN SMART ENVIRONMENT: CONCEPT AND OVERVIEW

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Abstract: The advent of the Internet of Things (IoT) has catalyzed a paradigm shift in the way we perceive and interact with our surroundings. This article comprehensively explores the concept of IoT in creating smart environments, delving into its fundamental components, applications across diverse sectors, challenges, and promising future trends. In this review article, we will provide a brief conception of environment areas of study based on IoT technology and discuss the justification behind using IoT in the field of environmental studies. Moreover, we will investigate many proposed applications of environmental research based upon IoT.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Smart Environment, IoT Components, IoT Applications, Challenges, Future Trends, Case Studies, IoT Impact.

The Internet of Things (IoT) represents a computing and communication model where everyday objects can connect to the internet. This connectivity involves integrating devices with limited resources, such as sensors and engines, along with intelligent systems that gather information from the physical world. This information is then processed for the control or management of various applications. The advantages of the internet extend to effective resource management, increased productivity, and an enhanced quality of life for individuals who can engage with intelligent environments like smart homes, health systems, cities, factories, or other human activities. Smart environmental sensor networks are designed to exhibit intelligent behavior, adapting to environmental conditions and power availability. These networks utilize nonstandard radio networking for communication, allowing

wireless gateways to route sensor data to the internet. In environmental IoT, nodes can possess internet connectivity, enabling them to directly transmit data to servers. This facilitates easier and more reliable interaction for users.

IoT Progressing Towards Smart Environments. The well-being of humans, as well as animals, birds, fish, and plants, is significantly influenced by the state of the environment and any adverse environmental conditions. This encompasses issues like environmental pollution, prompting extensive research endeavors aimed at addressing pollution-related problems and efficiently managing resources across various applications (refer to Figure 1). Establishing a healthy environment is a complex task due to factors such as industrial and transportation waste and irresponsible human activities contributing to environmental degradation on a daily basis. Monitoring the environment holds crucial importance for assessing its current state, making informed decisions based on collected data from monitoring systems. Efficient resource consumption and utilization, along with the reduction of industrial and vehicular waste, require effective management. Both monitoring and waste management generate substantial data, which is instrumental in establishing health standards by governmental or environmental organizations. This serves to protect both people and the environment, as well as to mitigate or prevent potential natural disasters.

Figure 1. Applications of environmental monitoring based on the Internet of Things

The effective monitoring and management of the environment, including waste management, necessitate intelligent techniques for communication and information exchange. This involves handling vast databases storing copious amounts of data collected from various monitoring devices and processing systems. These systems play a crucial role in making informed decisions to mitigate environmental issues such as water and air pollution, radiation, and natural disasters. The integration of wireless sensor networks, GPS, mobile and wireless communication technologies, databases, cloud storage, and the internet gives rise to what is commonly known as the Internet of Things (IoT). This integration facilitates easier collection and sharing of data and expedites decision-making processes in environmental monitoring and management. The IoT plays a pivotal role in providing continuous monitoring, particularly during critical situations such as disasters. With these capabilities, the IoT is increasingly becoming an integral part of environmental applications.

IoT-Enabled Environmental Monitoring. The Internet of Things (IoT) holds the potential to revolutionize various aspects of our daily lives, embedding microcontrollers in everyday objects and facilitating seamless communication between these objects and users over the internet. IoT plays a crucial role in monitoring and maintaining the quality of the environment by deploying sensors for pollution and quality across cities, with the collected sensor data being made accessible to the public. Technological advancements in wireless communication have given rise to pollution and quality monitoring sensors, as well as wireless networks for real-time monitoring and reporting. Environmental monitoring applications leveraging IoT typically utilize sensors to contribute to environmental protection by keeping track of air or water quality, atmospheric or soil conditions, and monitoring natural resources such as rivers, oceans, seas, and forests. Building an IoT-based environmental monitoring system involves integrating various devices, communication methods, technologies, and effective management and processing mechanisms into a cohesive system. In the subsequent sections, we will explore

different types of monitoring devices, communication technologies, and essential steps in constructing a remote monitoring environment system.

Monitoring Devices. Monitoring systems incorporate diverse devices that generate signals for various monitoring aspects. These signals are analyzed by electronic control and monitoring devices to provide relevant information to the machine's control unit or operator. Sensors, typically supported by Bluetooth or Wi-Fi, enable the collection of environmental data for monitoring and control purposes. The use of smartphone-embedded sensors, wearables, or devices placed in different locations introduces a new form of personal environmental sensors, revolutionizing the way data is collected, analyzed, and consumed. Various sensor models are employed for environmental monitoring, each designed for specific functions based on the type of environmental aspect being monitored. Examples of such sensor models include AirBot, WaterBot, Sensordrone, Air Quality Egg, Lapka, and wearable sensors.

A. AirBot Model. Developed by Carnegie Mellon University, this model monitors airborne pollutants that can impact respiratory health. Portable and easily carried, it allows individuals to monitor air quality wherever they go.

B. WaterBot Model. Designed for water quality monitoring, one end of this model can be immersed in a water source, uploading pollution data to the web through an integrated ZigBee module. The high-frequency data collection enables the detection of events invisible to other sensor types.

C. Sensordrone Model. This versatile tool senses various environmental factors, including gases, temperatures, and humidity, utilizing smartphones for data collection.

D. Lapka Model. Comprising environmental sensors that plug into smartphones, especially iPhones, Lapka can detect radiation, electromagnetic feedback, nitrates in raw foods, and provide data on temperature and humidity, contributing valuable insights on organic food.

E. Air Quality Egg. A home-based environmental sensor kit that provides high-resolution readings of NO₂ and CO concentrations, enhancing air quality monitoring wherever it is placed.

F. Electronic Nose Model. A multi-sensor device capable of detecting trace amounts of hazardous airborne chemicals, such as pesticides, combustion emissions, gas leaks, and chemical warfare agents.

In conclusion, IoT stands as a cornerstone for building smart environments that are not only connected but also intelligent and adaptive. The ongoing evolution of IoT technologies promises to redefine the way we live, work, and interact with the world around us.

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